

"23 TrainingThings": A Practical Guide for Effective Webinars in Research Data Management and Beyond

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Abstract

Effective formats for virtual knowledge transfer - such as online training sessions or webinars - are essential tools for supporting researchers, data stewards, and infrastructure providers. Particularly popular are hands-on training sessions that introduce concrete tools or methods. These are often conducted by subject-matter experts with deep technical knowledge. However, many of these experts have little formal training in educational methods or may not be fully aware of the diverse needs of their heterogeneous audience. As a result, content may be difficult for participants to grasp, and expectations may not be fully met. Poorly structured or insufficiently prepared webinars can not only hinder the adoption of a service but also negatively impact the reputation of a project or its presenters.

Drawing on extensive experience in delivering webinars, authors from various institutional backgrounds - including a state initiative and several NFDI consortia - collaborated to develop a practical resource that supports the design of effective webinars. The result is "**23 TrainingThings for Effective Webinars**", a compact, hands-on resource consisting of a **one-page checklist** and a **comprehensive extended guide**. These materials offer concrete guidance from defining learning objectives and structuring content to practical tips for moderation and interactive design. They are particularly aimed at subject-matter experts who want to share their knowledge in webinars while enhancing their skills in the didactic design of online training sessions.

This poster provides insights into 23 TrainingThings for Effective Webinars. Moreover, we aim to foster discussion on key questions: Which best practices have proven effective within the community? What common pitfalls should be avoided? And how can we constructively advise colleagues on delivering more effective webinars?

We invite the community to adopt, expand upon, and apply the **23 TrainingThings** concept in their own training initiatives.

Keywords: Knowledge Transfer; Online Training; Virtual Instructor-Led Training (VILT)

Resources

- [1] D. A. Hausen, S. Jordan, A. Manske and A. Schröter, „23 TrainingThings For Effective Webinars“, Zenodo, Feb. 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14792536>. “The guide serves as the foundation for this contribution, providing practical recommendations for planning, facilitating, and enhancing online training sessions.”

Author contributions

Daniela Hausen: Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

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Competing interests

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References

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